

Occupational Stressors of Teachers in the Department of Education Calbayog City Division

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ABSTRACT: Teaching is considered a noble profession. Despite being noble, it is considered demanding and stressful. This study was conducted to derive components that serve as occupational stressors of teachers in Calbayog City Division of the Department of Education. Three hundred and two teachers from Calbayog City Division of the Department of Education were identified by the researchers using random sampling technique. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test was applied to determine if Principal Component Analysis was appropriate for this study. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was used to know the strength of correlation between different variables. The researchers were able to identify four components as the stressors of teachers such as Motivation (Component 1), Cultural Professionalism (Component 2), Workload (Component 3), and Technology (Component 4).

KEYWORDS: Education, Performance, Stress, Teaching.

INTRODUCTION

Occupation is a necessity for a person to suffice the needs of the family. Having a good occupation helps a person have opportunity for many things such as social identity, income, and personal growth. However, it doesn't come without stress. According to Robat et al. (2021), "Stress is a psychological imbalance between perceptions of external demands and the internal resources available to meet those demands." This means that the work, management, and organization itself are not actually the ones producing stress, they only become stressors if there are poor resilience and ineffective strategies. No matter what the cause of occupational stress may be, its effects can be greatly damaging to an employee's well-being and productivity (bambooHR, 2022). With all these, both employees and organizations should consider that can hamper work motivation, dedication, and inspiration.

Teaching is considered a noble profession. There are a lot of competent teachers who can make quality education possible. These teachers become the main drivers in delivering productive work. However, if these teachers are bombarded with negativity in the workplace, they will not be able to perform well, leading to overall negative performance. Teaching as demanding profession is stressful. Stress affects the performance of employees. For teachers, workplace conditions are seen as prime factors contributing to stress. Stress leads to negative consequences such as poor morality, poor education quality, reduced student happiness, and absence (Cao et al., 2021). These negative consequences lead to poor overall performance of teachers. Having a negative performance is what should be avoided by the teachers. The study of Desouky & Allam (2017) in Egypt concluded that teaching is a highly stressful job which needs appropriate interventions by the authorities. We can say the same in the Philippines. In fact, the study of Manalo (2019) revealed that excessive work, time pressure, conflicting work demands, committee work involvement, insufficient space for activities are prime factors contributing to high level of stress of the teachers.

Occupational stress cannot be avoided. Quality of education is dependent on factors that contribute to the productivity of teachers. Occupational stress reduces the work quality of teachers. Desouky & Allam (2017) added that occupational stress leads to negative emotions impairing the ability to work well. Occupational stress provides a great risk for teachers. There are quite a number of researches conducted about stress in relation to occupation. Many of those studies are conducted outside the Philippines. There are a few studies related to teaching in Calbayog City. This study aimed to derive components that serve as occupational stressors of teachers in Calbayog City Division of the Department of Education.

METHODOLOGY

Design, Participants, and Sampling

The researchers employed descriptive research design in the conduct of this study. The participants of this study were both elementary and high school teachers from Calbayog City Division of the Department of Education (DepEd). The total population of teachers in Calbayog City Division was 2,284 during the conduct of this study. The sample size and actual participants were identified by applying random sampling technique using SPSS 28. The identified participants were 302. These identified participants were sent invitations to participate in the study. Once their acceptance was received, they were provided with questionnaires. These participants include ranks of teachers from Teacher 1, Teacher 2, Teacher 3, Head Teacher 1, Head Teacher 2, Head Teacher 3, Head Teacher 4, Head Teacher 5, Head Teacher 6, Master Teacher 1, Master Teacher 2, and Principal 1.

Data Collection & Analysis

The researchers made use of structured questionnaire to collect data from the participants. The questions/statements in the Likert Scale of the questionnaire were adopted from the previous study of the authors. Online sending of questionnaires were done because of the health restrictions in the area due to COVID-19. Once the participants were done answering the questionnaires, their answers were automatically saved via cloud storage. The data can only be accessed by authorized persons. The analysis of data was conducted using SPSS 28.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers will not be disclosing the names of the participants to protect them from inconveniences and harm to their social and professional identity. The researchers adhere to Republic Act 10173 otherwise known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012 of the Philippines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the profile of participants who participated in the conduct of this study.

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Participants

<i>TYPE OF SCHOOL</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>%</i>
Elementary	225	74.5%
Junior High School	19	6.3%
Senior High School	8	2.6%
Junior High School and Senior High School	49	16.2%
All Grade Levels are available	1	0.3%
<i>Total</i>	<i>302</i>	<i>100.0%</i>
<i>RANK OF TEACHER</i>		
Teacher 1	39	12.9%
Teacher 2	32	10.6%
Teacher 3	65	21.5%
Head Teacher 1	19	6.3%
Head Teacher 2	25	8.3%
Head Teacher 3	19	6.3%
Head Teacher 4	28	9.3%
Head Teacher 5	19	6.3%
Head Teacher 6	20	6.6%
Master Teacher 1	23	7.6%
Master Teacher 2	12	4.0%
Principal 1	1	0.3%
<i>Total</i>	<i>302</i>	<i>100.0%</i>

<i>YEARS OF SERVICE</i>		
Less than 1 year	17	5.6%
1 to 5 years	87	28.8%
6 to 10 years	45	14.9%
11 to 15 years	61	20.2%
16 to 20 years	54	17.9%
greater than 20 years	38	12.6%
<i>Total</i>	302	100.05
<i>GENDER</i>		
Female	136	45.0%
Male	96	31.8%
Prefer not to say	70	23.2%
<i>Total</i>	302	100.0%

Table 2 shows the mean standard deviation, and number of participants in the conduct of this study. The values of mean indicate the stressors of the participants.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Excessive Workload	302	1	5	4.32	.851
Work-Life Balance	302	1	5	3.52	1.262
Job Security	302	1	5	1.44	.860
Rate	302	1	5	3.61	1.184
Chance Promotion	302	1	5	1.82	1.206
Working Hours	302	1	5	4.32	.964
Management Style	302	1	5	2.39	1.190
Non-Cooperative Colleagues	302	1	5	2.43	1.047
Role Ambiguity	302	1	5	1.76	1.108
Insufficient Resources	302	1	5	4.03	1.076
Lack of Professionalism	302	1	5	2.42	1.120
Incentives	302	1	5	1.98	1.235
Work Against Values	302	1	4	1.46	.758
Keeping Up with Technology	302	1	5	2.57	1.296
Skills Requirement	302	1	5	2.26	1.099
High Client Demands	302	1	5	2.28	1.434
Poor Organizational Culture	302	1	5	2.41	1.122
Valid N (listwise)	302				

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett’s Test

Table 3 shows the results of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett’s Test. The KMO test was applied to identify the linear relationship index between the different variables. According to David & Fabillar (2022), the use of KMO test will help identify if Principal Component Analysis (herein referred to as PCA) is appropriate for this test. The KMO measure as shown in Table 3 is equal to 0.860 equivalent to “meritorious”. KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy indicates that the sample size of this study was adequate. Bartlett’s test of sphericity shows strong correlation between the different variables as indicated by positive significance (p-value < 0.000).

Table 3. KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.860
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2108.761
	df	136
	Sig.	.000

KMO Measure (Kaiser, 1974) : $KMO \geq 0.9$ = Marvelous
 $0.8 \leq KMO < 0.9$ = Meritorious
 $0.7 \leq KMO < 0.8$ = Middling
 $0.6 \leq KMO < 0.7$ = Mediocre
 $0.5 \leq KMO < 0.6$ = Miserable
 $KMO < 0.5$ = Unacceptable

Principal Component Analysis

The results of KMO and Bartlett's tests identified that PCA was an appropriate analysis for this study. The PCA identified the components considering the variables on the occupational stressors of teachers in Calbayog City.

Communalities

Table 4 shows the communalities of every variable accounted in the conduct of principal component analysis. This shows the variable variances comprised by the extracted factors. It can be seen in Table 4 the initial and extraction values of the variables. Among the variables, the highest are role ambiguity (75%), lack of professionalism (74.6%), high client demands (73.4%), and chance promotion (72.4%) while among the lowest are rate (33.2%), insufficient resources (42.8%), excessive workload (48.2%), and management style (55.9%).

Table 4. Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
Excessive Workload	1.000	.482
Work-Life Balance	1.000	.671
Job Security	1.000	.582
Rate	1.000	.332
Chance Promotion	1.000	.724
Working Hours	1.000	.574
Management Style	1.000	.559
Non-Cooperative Colleagues	1.000	.680
Role Ambiguity	1.000	.750
Insufficient Resources	1.000	.428
Lack of Professionalism	1.000	.746
Incentives	1.000	.683
Work Against Values	1.000	.644
Keeping Up with Technology	1.000	.574
Skills Requirement	1.000	.653
High Client Demands	1.000	.734
Poor Organizational Culture	1.000	.710

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Total Variance

Table 5 shows the values of components extracted from the conduct of PCA. This includes their eigenvalues, percent of variance, and cumulative variance of the components. A total of 5 components were derived with the use of PCA. The first component accounts for the 33.442% of the variance, the second for 11.6165% of the variance, the third for 8.913% of the variance,

and the fourth for 7.943% of the variance. The first four components were retained while the fifth to the seventeenth components were not.

Table 5. Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	of Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	of Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	of Cumulative %
1	5.685	33.442	33.442	5.685	33.442	33.442	3.927	23.098	23.098
2	1.975	11.616	45.059	1.975	11.616	45.059	2.748	16.165	39.263
3	1.515	8.913	53.972	1.515	8.913	53.972	2.023	11.903	51.166
4	1.350	7.943	61.914	1.350	7.943	61.914	1.827	10.749	61.914
5	.931	5.474	67.389						
6	.842	4.954	72.342						
7	.757	4.455	76.797						
8	.620	3.649	80.445						
9	.564	3.319	83.764						
10	.470	2.766	86.530						
11	.433	2.546	89.076						
12	.397	2.334	91.411						
13	.367	2.158	93.569						
14	.302	1.777	95.346						
15	.288	1.692	97.038						
16	.265	1.557	98.595						
17	.239	1.405	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The scree plot below shows the seventeen components as considered in the PCA. The scree plot shows the total variance of every eigenvalue versus its components. The researchers observed in the scree plot that the inflection point is on component four. All components beyond component four are considered non-significant.

Graph 1. Scree Plot

Rotated Component Matrix

Rotated component was also applied in this study to determine the factors that will be included in the different components. Table 6 shows the results of rotated component matrix, showing the number of components and the different factors loaded under them.

Table 6. Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
5. There is limited or even no chance to be promoted.	.820			
9. The purpose or the need of my role and tasks is ambiguous or unclear.	.784			
13. The tasks are against my values.	.767			
3. There is no job security.	.737			
12. There are no incentives available for our job level.	.725			
17. There is poor organizational culture in my workplace.		.821		
11. The people in my workplace lacks professionalism.		.810		
8. My colleagues are non-cooperative.		.779		
7. The management style of the head of unit or of the school is unfavorable.	.342	.659		
6. The regular working hours are long.			.683	
2. The work-life balance is difficult to achieve.	.375		.676	
1. The work is excessive.			.632	
4. The rate/payment is low or insufficient for personal needs.	.345		.457	
10. The resources needed for my tasks is insufficient.		.306	.442	.334
16. I cannot keep up with technology which is demanded in my job.				.744
15. My skills are insufficient for the demand of the job.	.418			.646
I cannot provide and cope up with the high demands of my clients.	.487			.632

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

Derived Components

After applying the Principal Component Analysis, the researchers were able to derive to four components. These components are reflected in table 7.

Table 7. Derived Component

Component	Variables	Component Loading
Component 1	5. There is limited or even no chance to be promoted.	.820
	9. The purpose or the need of my role and tasks is ambiguous or unclear.	.784
	13. The tasks are against my values.	.767
	3. There is no job security.	.737
	12. There are no incentives available for our job level.	.725
Component 2	17. There is poor organizational culture in my workplace.	.821
	11. The people in my workplace lacks professionalism.	.810
	8. My colleagues are non-cooperative.	.779
Component 3	6. The regular working hours are long.	.683
	1. The work is excessive.	.632
Component 4	16. I cannot keep up with technology which is demanded in my job.	.744

Component 1 (Motivation) included five items with factor loading for 0.820, 0.784, 0.767, 0.737, and 0.725 (items 5, 9, 13, 3, and 12).

Component 2 (Cultural Professionalism) included three items with factor loading 0.821, 0.810, and 0.779 (items 17, 11, and 8).

Component 3 (Workload) included two items with factor loading 0.683 and 0.632 (items 6 and 1).

Component 4 (Technology) included one item with factor loading 0.744 (item 16)

The factors with values less than 0.5 component loading and appeared in more than one component were not included in the principal components.

CONCLUSION

The conduct of PCA identified four components. These four components are Motivation (Component 1), Cultural Professionalism (Component 2), Workload (Component 3), and Technology (Component 4).

Motivation (Component 1)

The teachers will become more motivated if they perceived that they have greater chances for promotion and clear purpose of their role in their own organization aside from teaching. The teachers also tend to be less motivated if some of the tasks are against their values. Though the teachers who answered the questionnaires are from public schools, they still perceive that they do not have job security. Teachers also answered that they receive no incentives for their job level from their respective schools.

Cultural Professionalism (Component 2)

The teachers see that there is a poor organizational culture, lack of professionalism, and non-cooperative colleagues in their workplace. There is a need to improve the organizational culture of the DepEd teachers in Calbayog City. By improving the organizational culture, there will be a greater chance that the productivity of teacher will increase. The teachers will be more engaged in their tasks if there is a healthy organizational culture. A professional development training may be conducted to improve professionalism in the organization. Some teachers are non-cooperative. If some teachers continue to being non-cooperative, reduced productivity and job dissatisfaction would likely happen. Teachers should cooperate with each other to have a more effective workplace.

Workload (Component 3)

Teachers in Calbayog City work longer hours than the required time. Working longer hours may have negative effects to the health of teachers. As stated by Picincu (2019), "A heavy workload also affects their mood and behavior, causing poor mental focus, decreased motivation and difficulty concentrating on the tasks at hand." Excessive workload is one of the several factors contributing to occupational stress. Excessive workload leads to reduction of work performance. It is important that teachers manage their workloads well and school management should see to it that the teachers are doing well doing the tasks given to them. Oftentimes, the higher-ups become contributors to excessive workload of teachers.

Technology (Component 4)

The existence of technology used for teaching does not mean it is effectively used and managed by teachers. The results of this study shows that many teachers cannot keep up with the technology in teaching. The use of technology is highly necessary nowadays especially in doing distance learning. Technology keeps evolving and it is becoming hard for teachers to cope up especially those who are already nearing the age of retirement.

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